

Application of Good Governance Principles In the Management of the Covid-19 Social Assistance Fund in Majalaya Village, Bandung Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This research was motivated by the ineffect management target of Covid-19 social assistance funds and was not in accordance with the principles of good governance. This research aims to find out the application of the principles of good governance in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village, Bandung Regency. This research uses a type of qualitative descriptive research. This research was conducted at the Majalaya Village Government office, Bandung Regency in 2021. The data collection in this study used interview, observation and documentation techniques. The data analysis technique used by this study is a triangulation analysis. From this research, it is expected to get an overview of the processing of Covid-19 social assistance funds with the principles of good governance. From research on the five principles that researchers observe, namely the principles of community participation, transparency, equality and justice, effectiveness and efficiency, and accountability can be concluded that the Application of The Principles of Good Governance in the Management of Covid-19 Social Assistance Fund in Majalaya Village of Bandung Regency is quite good on the principle of community participation, effectiveness and efficiency, equality and justice, and accountability. But there are still shortcomings in the principles of transparency.

KEYWORDS- Covid-19, Majalaya Village, Principles of Good Governance, and Social Assistance Fund Management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Corona virus or better known as Covid-19 is a type of virus that attacks human respiration and can cause death. The first positive case of Covid-19 was found in Indonesia on March 2, 2020, which attacked two Depok residents who were infected from a Japanese citizen. Then quickly Covid-19 spread throughout Indonesia with very easy transmission. This disease is spread through small droplets from the nose or mouth when coughing or sneezing which if they fall on surrounding objects and then touch another person, then the person touches the eyes, nose and mouth or accidentally inhales the virus from the sufferer. The Covid-19 virus has initial symptoms such as fever, cough, runny nose, respiratory problems, sore throat, and lethargy (Ministry of Health, 2020).

Responding to the increasing number of Covid-19 cases in Indonesia, the government continues to make efforts to prevent and control the spread of this virus by issuing policies, among others, establishing the Covid-19 outbreak as a non-natural national disaster through Presidential Decree of the Republic of Indonesia number 2 of 2020 concerning Determination of Non-Natural Disasters. -Natural. The government has also implemented Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) for areas that are included in the red zone by stipulating the Minister of Health Regulation (Permenkes) Number 9 of 2020 concerning PSBB guidelines. The government has also implemented a policy of working at home, studying at home, and worshipping at home, as well as an appeal to keep distance and reduce crowds to reduce the number of Covid-19 spreads (Government, 2020).

From this government policy, there are barriers for people who work to earn daily income and have an impact on meeting family needs. The situation without sources of income and loss of income results in an increase in poverty rates. These economic problems have prompted the Indonesian government to issue a policy by providing social assistance (bansos) to underprivileged communities and workers whose income has been affected by Covid-19 through Minister of Home Affairs Regulation (Permendagri) Number 20 of 2020 concerning Handling Covid-19. In its implementation, the government provides assistance in the form of Cash Social Assistance (BST), and Direct Cash Assistance (BLT). Cash Social Assistance (BST) in accordance with the Circular Letter of the Republic of Indonesia KPK No. 11 of 2020, namely in the form of basic necessities or cash. Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) is sourced from the allocation of village funds in the Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBDes). The management of Covid-19 social assistance funds can be carried out optimally if it is supported by a good governance system. The concept of governance that is very popular among the government today is the concept of good governance. The concept of good governance includes the principles of: 1) community participation, 2) law enforcement, 3) transparency, 4) responsiveness, 5) consensus orientation, 6) justice/equality, 7) effectiveness and efficiency, 8) accountability, and 9) strategic vision (KPK, 2016).

With an understanding of the theory of governance on governance theoretically and practically, it is very important to rebuild the government system by changing the public policy model and eliminating practices in all respects that are inefficient and cause many failures or losses in government administration (Yu Keping, 2017).

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research belongs to the type of descriptive research using qualitative approach method, namely the type of research that the findings are not obtained from quantification data in the form of numbers and do not use statistical calculation procedures (Sugiyono, 2013). The type of data used in this study is primary data obtained directly from related parties who are the main source of information and secondary data, which is obtained from data commonly used by related organizations. Secondary data was obtained from reviewing documents such as news, policies, and financial reports of the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village. The data collection technique used in this research is the interview, observation and documentation methods. The data analysis technique used in this research is triangulation analysis which consists of 4 processes, namely: 1) describing the sources, 2) describing the information obtained from the informants, 3) comparing the theory with information from the informants, and 4) conclusions and recommendation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1.1 Overview of Research Objects

Majalaya Village is one of the 11 (eleven) villages in Indonesia Majalaya District, Bandung Regency. Majalaya village is the mother village of Majasetra and Majakerta Villages, through Village Expansion on 22 July Year 1977. Majalaya Village is located around the PasarBingung Majalaya precisely on Jalan Station no. 22-24, Majalaya, Majalaya District, Bandung Regency. To achieve the goal of a good and prosperous village, the Majalaya Village government refers to the vision and mission that have been set, as follows:

Vision

“The realization of a Clean, Religious, Prosperous, and Neat Majalaya Village community and Beautiful through the Acceleration of Development based on Religion, Culture Legal and Environmentally oriented with improvement Apparatus Performance and Community Empowerment.

Mission

In realizing the vision of Majalaya Village, the following missions and programs are implemented:

1. Long-Term Development

- Continuing village development that has not been implemented.
- Increase cooperation between village government and existing village institutions.
- Improving the welfare of rural communities by improving facilities and infrastructure economic infrastructure of the people.

2. Short-Term Development

- Develop and maintain and preserve village customs, especially those that has taken root in the village of Majalaya.
- Improving services in the field of government to citizens - Improving the economic facilities and infrastructure of villagers by improving infrastructure and economic means.
- Improving educational facilities and infrastructure in order to increase resources Majalaya Village people.

In implementing the realization of the mission and work program, Majalaya Village is guided by: on the 1945 Constitution and other regulations that have been stipulated. Along With the times, the Majalaya Village government has a legal basis as follows :

1. Regional Regulation No. 12 of 2016 concerning the Formation and Composition of Regional Apparatus.
2. Permendagri No. 84 of 2015 concerning Organizational Structure and Work Procedures Village government.
3. Perbup No. 31 of 2017 concerning Implementation Guidelines for Regional Regulations Bandung Regency Number 10 of 2016 concerning Village Government Organizations.
4. Perbup No. 8 of 2017 concerning Amendments to Regent Regulation Number 25 2016.

From the legal basis that is used as a guide in the implementation of governance village development, Majalaya Village has an organizational structure to facilitate coordination of each village apparatus in carrying out their duties and functions properly. The following structure is owned by the Majalaya Village Government:

Figure 1 Village Organizational Structure

1.2 Research Results

The management of Covid-19 social assistance funds is a very interesting element to research and observe during a pandemic like this, especially in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village, Majalaya District, Bandung Regency. The focus of this research is on the application of good governance principles in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village, Majalaya District, Bandung Regency. The application of the principles of good governance examined and observed in this study consisted of 5 principles, namely the principle of community participation, the principle of transparency, the principle of equality or justice, the principle of effectiveness and efficiency, and the principle of accountability. The results of the study are based on observations and interviews with several officials and the Majalaya Village community regarding the application of the five principles of good governance in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds, as follows:

1. Community Participation

Participation from the community is important in managing the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village because the data and votes provided from the community make it easier for Majalaya Village to collect data on anyone who is underprivileged and affected by Covid and needs assistance from the government. The application of the principle of community participation in the management of the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village has been quite good, as can be seen from the participation of a deliberation program between the Majalaya Village government and the local community. The Majalaya Village in collaboration with RT and RW created a Whatsapp group facility with the entire community. The Majalaya Village Government involves the community as officers for distributing Covid-19 social assistance funds.

2. Transparency

The principle of transparency is very important in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village to create openness and mutual trust between Majalaya Village parties and the Majalaya Village community. The application of the principle of transparency in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village has already been implemented, as can be seen from the banner in front of the Village Office regarding the amount of the aid budget. In distributing the Covid-19 social assistance funds, the Majalaya Village government calculated the amount of money that would be received in front of the beneficiaries without being covered. The rice that will be distributed is shown directly in front of all beneficiaries. Each distribution of aid funds, all RT and RW accompany to monitor the citizens who receive assistance. However, the application of the principle of transparency in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village is still lacking in the reporting field. Reports regarding these funds are only known for sure by the Village Secretary and such reports and financial records are not allowed to be viewed or requested.

3. Equality or Justice

The principle of equality must be upheld in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village in order to create justice for all Majalaya Village communities. The application of the principle of equality or justice in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village is quite good, as can be seen from the appropriate distribution of Covid-19 social assistance funds to people who can't afford and are affected by Covid-19 so they don't have difficulties. Recipients of assistance are sorted by the village to find out which ones need help and which ones don't.

4. Effectiveness and Efficiency

The principles of effectiveness and efficiency are important in managing the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village so that its objectives can be achieved properly, carefully, and on target. The application of the principles of effectiveness and efficiency in the management of the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village has been quite good, as can be seen from the general objectives that have been achieved.

5. Accountability

The principle of accountability is very important to apply in the management of the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village so that every task and function of each part in the management of the aid fund can be accounted for. The application of the principle of accountability in the management of the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village is quite good, it can be seen from each party in managing the aid fund carrying out their duties and functions properly in accordance with the objectives and orders of the Village Head.

These are the completeness in managing the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village:

No	Mechanism	Done	Is Not Done
1	Account opening for social assistance recipients.	√	
2	Deliberation between the Village Government and the Majalaya Village community.	√	
3	Distribution of beneficiary Family Cards.	√	
4	Withdrawal of aid funds from the center to Majalaya Village.	√	
5	The process of distributing aid to the Majalaya Village community.	√	
6	Reconciliation of results of distribution of social assistance funds.	√	
7	Reporting on the distribution of Covid-19 social assistance funds.	√	

Table 1 Table of completeness of procedures for distributing COVID-19 social assistance funds

1.3 Discussions

This research is in line with previous research by Badrus Zaman (2020) entitled "Application of Good Governance Principles in the Management of Village Fund Allocation (Study in Kampungbaru Village, Kepung District, Kediri Regency)". The results of previous studies concluded that in general the Kampungbaru Village was in accordance with the principles of Good Governance, but technically there were still obstacles. It is the same as in Majalaya Village, 4 (three) of the 5 (five) principles have worked well but are still not good at the principle of transparency.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1.4 Conclusions

From the results of the study it can be concluded as follows:

1. The application of the principle of community participation in the management of the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village is quite good. The Majalaya Village Government also attracted the community in the discussion regarding the Covid-19 social assistance fund. The Majalaya Village Government also made facilities in the form of Whatsapp groups for all RT, RW and the community.
2. The application of the principle of transparency in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village is still lacking. The application of the principle of transparency that has been carried out by the Majalaya Village government is that it is quite open about the Covid-19 social assistance funds that will be given to beneficiaries. The Majalaya Village Government put up a banner in front of the Village Office regarding the amount of the budget that had fallen. However, in the reporting section there is no transparency from the Majalaya Village government. The Majalaya Village Government did not show a report regarding the Covid-19 social assistance fund, even the one who knew for sure about the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village was only the Majalaya Village Secretary.
3. The application of the principles of equality and justice in the management of the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village is good. The Majalaya Village Government only provides assistance to people who are underprivileged and affected by Covid-19 and does not provide such assistance to people who are well off and not affected by Covid-19.
4. The implementation of the principles of effectiveness and efficiency in the management of the Covid-19 social assistance fund in Majalaya Village is good. The aid fund management officer has achieved his

goal of providing targeted aid funds according to the data on recipients of Covid-19 social assistance that has been recorded in the recipient data.

5. The application of the principle of accountability in the management of Covid-19 social assistance funds in Majalaya Village is still not good. The Majalaya Village Government and the management of the Covid-19 social assistance fund carry out their duties and functions properly in accordance with the objectives and orders of the Village Head.

1.5 Recommendations

The researcher's suggestions for Majalaya Village in applying the principles of good governance in managing Covid-19 social assistance funds are as follows:

1. In applying the principle of community participation, the Majalaya Village government should increase its activity in inviting the community to take part in deliberation activities. The Majalaya Village community also needs to have self-awareness to participate in every program carried out by Majalaya Village including the management of the Covid-19 social assistance fund.
2. In the application of the principle of transparency, the Majalaya Village government is required to maintain and even increase the transparency of financial reporting and records regarding all funds that go down to every Majalaya Village community who is included as a recipient of assistance.
3. In applying the principles of equality and justice, the Majalaya Village government should improve performance in collecting data on the poor and affected by Covid so that no community data is missed to receive assistance.
4. In applying the principles of effectiveness and efficiency, the Majalaya Village government is to improve performance in directing the goals of the Covid-19 social assistance fund properly and on target and there are no people who are unable and affected by the pandemic who are not registered as beneficiaries.
5. In applying the principle of accountability, the Majalaya Village government should improve the monitoring of the performance of all parts of the Majalaya Village government in carrying out their respective duties and functions.

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